

Online Condition Monitoring for Resonant Tank Capacitors in LLC Converters Using Voltage Gain

Sen Tan, Wenfa Kang, Jingxuan Wu, Juan C. Vasquez, Josep M. Guerrero, Baoze Wei Aalborg University

Project Description and Objectives

Hybrid Electric regional Aircraft distribution Technologies (HECATE) aims to deliver transformative technologies to electrical distribution for future Hybrid Electric Aircraft. Task is given to evaluate the PHM for LLC power converter and life cycle assessment.

The Metallized Polypropylene Film Capacitors (MPPF-Caps) is a critical yet vulnerable component in power electronic converters. Monitoring capacitance is crucial for predicting the lifespan of MPPF capacitors.

This paper introduces a **monitoring scheme** specifically for LLC resonant capacitor that estimates the capacitance of its capacitor on the output side.

Methodology

A. Condition monitoring

	Al-Caps	MPPF-Caps	MLC-Caps
EOL criteria	$C/C_0 < 80\%$	$C/C_0 < 95\%$	$C/C_0 < 90\%$

B. Calculation model

Primary Voltage: $V_{ac} = \frac{2n}{\pi} V_{in} \sin(2\pi f_s t)$

Secondary Voltage: $V_{rec} = \frac{4N}{\pi} V_o \sin(2\pi f_s t - \psi_v)$

Voltage Gain: $M = \frac{V_{rec}}{V_{ac}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{[(1 - \frac{1}{f_n^2})Qf_n]^2 + [(1 - \frac{1}{f_n^2})\frac{1}{K} + 1]^2}}$

Cap Estimation:

$$\hat{C}_r = \frac{1}{4L_r\pi^2 f_s^2 \left(1 - \frac{L_m Z_{eq} (\sqrt{-4L_m^2 M^2 \pi^2 f_s^2 + X_{eq}^2} - M Z_{eq})}{L_r M X_{eq}^2}\right)}$$

C. Algorithm representation

Algorithm 1: The proposed capacitance estimation approach for MPPF-Caps in resonant tank.

Input: Resonant tank parameters L_r, L_m . Input and output voltage measurements of LLC converter V_{in}, V_o .

Output: Estimated capacitance \hat{C}_r .

1. Generate reference resonant frequency using VCO.
2. Calculate the secondary impedance.
3. Determine the voltage gain of the resonant tank.
4. Estimate the MPPF-Cap capacitance with proposed approach outlined.

Results

LLC converter parameters, setups

Rated input voltage	24 V
Rated output voltage	20 V
Rated power	96 W
Turns ratio N	5:1
Resonant inductance L_r	$6.5 \mu H$
Magnetizing inductance L_m	$32.9 \mu H$
Resonant capacitance C_r	$1.54 \mu F$
Resonant frequency	50 kHz

